

Extracting dynamic topography using river longitudinal profiles and cosmogenic nuclide geochronology in the Middle Atlas and the High Plateaus of Morocco

Alvar Pastor^{a*}, Julien Babault^a, Lewis A. Owen^b, Antonio Teixell^a, Maria-Luisa Arboleya^a

^a *Departament de Geologia, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, E-08193, Bellaterra, Spain*

^b *Department of Geology, University of Cincinnati, Cincinnati, OH 45221, USA*

* *Corresponding author. Tel.: +569 93830679.*

E-mail address: alvarpastorc@gmail.com (A. Pastor).

ABSTRACT

The Moulouya river has intensely eroded the Arhbalou, Missouri, and Guercif Neogene foreland basins in northeastern Morocco, that changed from net aggradation during the Miocene-early Pliocene to net incision punctuated by alluvial fan deposition in the late Pliocene or the early Quaternary. This region has experienced mantle-driven, long-wavelength surface uplift (dynamic topography) during the late Cenozoic and is locally affected by uplift due to crustal shortening and thickening of the Middle Atlas. Knickpoints of several hundred meters high are located along major drainages of the Moulouya fluvial network, being present on both the undeformed margins of the Missouri and Guercif foreland basins (High Plateaus) and along the thrust margin of southern Middle Atlas front, where they reach heights of 800-1000 m. From the stable margin it can be inferred that 500-550 m of the knickpoint heights might be explained by long-wavelength dynamic uplift, whereas the remaining 450-500 m in the southern Middle Atlas front and 200-300 m in the northeastern edge of the Middle Atlas are related to thrust-related uplift of the Jebel Bou Naceur. ¹⁰Be terrestrial cosmogenic nuclide (TCN) dating of two Quaternary river terraces in the Chegg Ard valley to 62±14 ka and 411±55 ka. These dated terraces allow the rates of incision associated with the frontal structures

of the Middle Atlas that emerge within the Missouri basin, with respect to the undeformed surface of the basin, to be estimated to be in the order of $\sim 0.3 \text{ mm a}^{-1}$. The background incision rate due to mantle-driven regional uplift since the Middle Pleistocene is estimated to be in the order of $\sim 0.1\text{-}0.2 \text{ mm.a}^{-1}$ for the central part of the Missouri basin.

Keywords

Atlas Mountains; foreland basin; river profile; knickpoint; cosmogenic dating; neotectonics; dynamic topography.

1. Introduction

The thrusts belts of the Atlas Mountains of Morocco and the surrounding plains underwent long-wavelength surface uplift caused by thermal buoyancy within the mantle during the late Cenozoic (Teixell *et al.*, 2003; 2005; Zeyen *et al.*, 2005; Babault *et al.*, 2008). Deformation of drainage networks and geomorphic indexes suggest that doming is still active (Barbero *et al.*, 2011; Barcos *et al.*, 2014). This mantle-driven surface uplift is superimposed onto the effect of the thickened crust of the High and Middle Atlas produced by thrusting since the Paleogene. Although tectonic shortening is moderate in the Atlas thrust belts, neotectonic deformation registered in Quaternary alluvial deposits at the southern fronts of the High and Middle Atlas indicates that thrusting is also still active (Sebrier *et al.*, 2006; Laville *et al.*, 2007; Delcaillau *et al.*, 2007; Pastor *et al.*, 2012).

Within this framework, the landscape of the Arhbalou, Missouri, and Guercif basins, the foreland basins of the High and Middle Atlas in northeastern Morocco (Fig. 1), changed from a state of net aggradation to a state of erosion and fluvial incision in the late Pliocene or Quaternary (Bouazza *et al.*, 2009). These basins are currently drained by the Moulouya river network, a large network the headwaters of which are in the flanking reliefs of the Middle Atlas, the High Atlas, and the High Plateaus (Fig. 1). The basins are only deformed in the proximity of the High and Middle Atlas thrust fronts, and, together with the flanking mountain belts, provide a useful natural laboratory to examine the drivers of landscape change and, in particular, the rates of different sources of uplift.

This work presents a tectonic and geomorphic study of the Arhbalou, Missouri and southern Guercif basins and of their eastern and western margins, featuring an analysis of the longitudinal profiles of the main tributaries composing the upper Moulouya river drainage network. The analysis of river long profiles reveals the systematic presence of large knickpoints or knickzones on tributaries draining both flanks of the Moulouya river, that is, the folded Middle Atlas and the undeformed High Plateaus, enabling a discussion on the origin of knickpoints and suggesting that in the study case they are largely associated with regional-scale phenomena, as mantle-related surface uplift.

We present the first ^{10}Be terrestrial cosmogenic nuclide (TCN) dating of Quaternary deposits within the Missouri basin allowing the determination of rates of fluvial incision since the Middle Pleistocene and estimate of uplift rates. Combined with the geomorphic analysis, the geochronological data allow us to assess the role of different drivers of uplift in the landscape evolution of the northeastern Atlas region. Other studies elsewhere attempted to retrieve magnitudes of mantle-driven uplift from geomorphic indicators (e.g., Nereson *et al.*, 2013; Paul *et al.*, 2014; Schilgen *et al.*, 2012). This study intends, for the first time, to discriminate the amount and rate of river incision directly related with tectonic deformation from those associated with the regional, mantle-driven dynamic topography.

2. Regional setting

The Moulouya river (~ 650 km-long) is, after the Nile, the second largest river in North Africa that drains to the Mediterranean Sea (Fig. 1). From its headwaters to the basin outlet, the Moulouya river flows across the Arhbalou, Missouri, and Guercif Neogene foreland basins and drains an area of ~ 74,000 km², including the High Plateaus in the east, the High Atlas in the south, the Middle Atlas towards the west, and the eastern Rif in the north-west, to eventually enter the Mediterranean sea near Nador in northern Morocco. The Moulouya river begins at 2,000 m asl at the junction of the Middle and High Atlas, which is the drainage divide between rivers flowing to the Atlantic and to the Mediterranean. The course of the Moulouya river, from its headwaters to the Mediterranean Sea, is at least twice the distance from its headwaters to the Atlantic, and

for that reason slopes are steeper on the Atlantic side where headward eroding rivers threaten to capture the upper part of the Moulouya catchment.

The geologic evolution of the Arhbalou and Missouri sedimentary basins is related to the thrust loading of the Cenozoic High and Middle Atlas orogenic belts (Beauchamp *et al.*, 1996; Arboleya *et al.*, 2004), whereas the Guercif basin has been influenced by the Rif orogen (Gomez *et al.*, 2000). The Arhbalou, Missouri and Guercif basins are filled mostly with Miocene alluvial and lacustrine sediments. The sedimentary record has been described in detail by Bernini *et al.* (1999; 2000), Gomez *et al.* (2000), Krijgsman and Langereis (2000) and Sani *et al.* (2000) for the Guercif basin, by Beauchamp *et al.* (1996) and Ellouz *et al.* (2003) for the Missouri basin, and by Dutour (1983) for the Arhbalou basin. Bouazza *et al.* (2009) proposed that basin sedimentation in the Guercif basin ended in the early Quaternary when the basin could have changed from being endorheic to externally drained, connecting the Moulouya river to the Mediterranean Sea.

The southern Middle Atlas front defines the western margin of the Missouri basin. The Middle Atlas is a NE- trending, basement-involved thrust belt that derives from the inversion of a Triassic-Jurassic rift, with a relatively simple structure and a modest amount of total orogenic shortening (<10%, Gomez *et al.*, 1998, Arboleya *et al.*, 2004). In the mountain front, Jurassic rocks of the Middle Atlas overthrust Tertiary and Quaternary conglomerates at the foot of Jebel Bou Naceur range (jebel is Moroccan for mountain) (Fig. 1). The Jebel Bou Naceur range forms a mountain ridge with a maximum elevation of 3356 m asl., rising ~2,500 m above the Moulouya basin, and limited by a southeastern facing topographic scarp that Delcaillau *et al.* (2007) interpreted as an active fault zone. The Neogene basin fill onlaps the undeformed Jurassic bedrock of the High Plateaus on the eastern margin of the Missouri basin. Plio-Pleistocene lacustrine deposits overlap much of the Jurassic carbonates of the High Plateaus. The timing of initial thrusting at Jebel Bou Naceur is unknown, but according to Laville *et al.* (2007) the thrust system was active during the Neogene, when Mesozoic rocks were thrust over fluvial-alluvial rocks of the Bou Irhardaiene Formation. According to paleomagnetic data reported by Krijgsman and Langereis (2000), the Bou Irhardaiene Formation was deposited until the lower Pliocene (Zanclean). Thrust-related folding occurs in the northwestern margin of the basin and deforms the Bou Irhardaiene Formation and

Quaternary alluvial gravels; the gravels are unconformable in places (Delcaillau *et al.*, 2007).

The mean elevation of the Middle Atlas mountains (between 1500 and 2000 m over large areas) contrasts with the crustal thickness under the mountains, recently determined in ca. 32 km by a wide-angle seismic survey (Ayarza *et al.*, 2014). The relatively thin crust suggests a modest degree of crustal thickening during the Atlas orogeny, consistent with the amount of shortening observed, and provides support to the view that the crust is not in isostatic equilibrium at the crustal level. To explain the discrepancy between shortening and elevation and other geologic features as the occurrence of significant volumes of alkaline magmatism of Neogene age, the subcrustal structure was investigated by means of potential-field modeling, which indicated that the lithosphere was thin (<90 km) under the Middle Atlas mountains and the Arhbalou-Missour basins (Teixell *et al.*, 2005; Zeyen *et al.*, 2005; Fullea *et al.*, 2010), an inference recently supported by seismological data (Miller and Becker, 2014; Palomeras *et al.*, 2014). Hence, the surface uplift of the Atlas region is ascribed to two components: a component of crustal isostasy, related to (modest) thickness variations of the crust during the Atlas orogeny, and a component related to changes in mantle buoyancy, probably due to an asthenospheric upwelling (which was described as dynamic topography by Teixell *et al.*, 2005, and Sun *et al.*, 2014). The first component is circumscribed to the High and Middle Atlas deformed belts, whereas the second is of longer wavelength and affects also the peripheral high plains as the Arhbalou and Missouri basins. On the basis of unconformable, Messinian-age marine deposits at high altitude, Babault *et al.*, (2008) estimated the magnitude of mantle-driven rock uplift in the Middle Atlas is ~1000 m, which thus took place after the Miocene. Geomorphic indexes from the lower Moulouya river area led Barcos *et al.* (2014) to suggest that this component of uplift is still active.

3. Methods

3.1. Knickpoints and paleoprofile reconstruction

The construction of the river longitudinal profiles shown in this paper used the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with 90 m of pixel resolution provided by the Shuttle Radar

Topography Mission (SRMT) from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA).

The term knickpoint describes an abrupt change in river gradient, which creates a local convexity in the generally concave-up equilibrium longitudinal profile of a river (Whipple and Tucker, 1999). The term knickzone is used when the convex segment of the river longitudinal profile persists along many kilometers. In our analysis, we consider the vertical component of knickpoint migration as equivalent to the relative base level fall, what can be deduced by comparing the current longitudinal profile with a reconstructed past hypothetical ideal longitudinal profile (paleoprofile). Therefore, we use paleo-longitudinal river profiles as a proxy for rock uplift. A paleo-longitudinal river profile can be determined using the longitudinal profile equation for rivers using the method described by Hoke *et al.* (2007). This method relies on the study of a river segment bounded by a knickpoint. The knickpoint separates an unmodified upstream reach from a downstream segment that adapts its slope to the new boundary conditions imposed by the relative base level fall (Whipple and Tucker, 1999; Bishop, 2007). Increased fluvial incision propagates upward along the channel and causes the headward/upstream advance of the knickpoint. It is assumed that the upper trunk (headwater from the knickpoint) already corresponds to a river's longitudinal profile that was adjusted to a state prior to the relative fall of the base level, where the inferred rock uplift is not underestimated by the river incision. Under these assumptions, the empirical power-law gradient-area relationship (Flint, 1974; Howard and Kerby, 1983) and the relationship between downstream distance, x , and cumulative drainage area (Hack, 1957) can be used to reconstruct a river paleo-longitudinal river profile from the equation of a longitudinal river profile elevation (Whipple and Tucker, 1999; Whipple, 2001). As such the elevation z , at a distance x from the drainage divide is

$$z(x) = k_s k_a^{-\theta} (1-h\theta)^{-1} (L^{1-h\theta} - x^{1-h\theta}) + z(L) \quad h \neq 1; \quad x_c \leq x \leq L; \quad \text{eq. 1}$$

where L is the distance from the outlet to the drainage divide, x_c is the distance from the divide at which fluvial processes become dominant over hillslope processes, k_s is the steepness index, θ is the concavity index, k_a is Hack's (1957) coefficient and h is Hack's (1957) exponent. The difference in elevation between the reconstructed profile (paleo-longitudinal river profile) above and the modern downstream segment at the outlet

elevation gives the knickpoint height. We reconstructed the unmodified upstream segment (inherited from the old boundary conditions), which allowed us to obtain values for k_s and θ for the best fit to the upper segment, and projecting these values to the downstream segment, affected by the new boundary conditions.

3.2. Surface dating

We dated two alluvial fan/terrace surfaces (T1 and T2) in the Chegg Ard valley, draining the Middle Atlas to the Missouri basin. The surfaces dated in this study were mostly composed of limestone and dolomite, with minor amounts of sandstone and phyllite, pebbles and cobbles, and occasional small boulders. We selected cobbles of sandstone and phyllite from surfaces for ^{10}Be TCN dating. Sampled surfaces are flat and extensive, not affected by topographic shielding. Samples were collected from sites far enough from slopes in order to minimize material gained from upper levels. We also selected sampling sites that showed little evidence of erosion, generally in areas where there were well-developed rock varnish. The size of sampled rocks were 5-10 cm in height and 10-20 cm its long segment. The condition of the sampled surfaces, sample rock type, topographic shielding, and position of all samples were recorded and are presented in Table 1. The detailed description of the terrace surfaces is addressed below (see section 5).

Samples were prepared in the TCN Geochronology Laboratories at the University of Cincinnati. About 500 g of each sample was crushed and sieved to obtain 250–500 μm fraction from which quartz was separated using the methods of Kohl and Nishiizumi (1992). Be carrier was added to each sample, and by means of an ion exchange chromatography technique, Be was separated, purified and precipitated as $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ at a pH of 7. The $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ gel was calcinated by ignition at 750 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 min in quartz crucibles. The resultant BeO was mixed with Nb powder and loaded into steel targets. $^{10}\text{Be}/^9\text{Be}$ ratios were measured using accelerator mass spectrometry at the Purdue Rare Isotope Measurement Laboratory at Purdue University. Isotope ratios were compared with ICN Pharmaceutical Incorporated ^{10}Be and NIST (National Institute Standard of Technology) standards prepared by K. Nishiizumi (pers. comm.).

Ages were calculated using the CRONUS-Earth online calculator Version 2.2 applying appropriate ^{10}Be standardizations (Balco *et al.*, 2008) with a sea-level high latitude

(SLHL) production rate of 4.49 ± 0.39 ^{10}Be atoms g^{-1} of quartz y^{-1} , a ^{10}Be half-life of 1.36×10^6 years (Nishiizumi *et al.*, 2007) and using a rock density of 2.75 g cm^{-3} with zero-erosion rate.

There is currently much debate regarding the appropriate scaling models and geomagnetic corrections for TCN production to calculate surface exposure ages (e.g. Pigati and Lifton 2004; Staiger *et al.* 2007; Balco *et al.* 2008). We present ages for all scaling models, but choose to use the time-dependent scaling factors of Lal (1991) and Stone (2000) in our discussion (Table 1). However, we are aware that other scaling models would produce ages that may be up to 10% older (Table 1).

3.3. *Quantifying rates of fluvial incision and deformation*

Incised fluvial surfaces allow rates of fluvial incision (I) to be estimated using the age (A) and height (h) of the surface with respect to the current river, such that $I=A/h$ (e.g., Burbank and Anderson, 2001). In this work, the absolute elevation of the terrace surfaces (h) were obtained from the SRTM90 DEM, whose precision is optimal when measuring surfaces with slopes $< 10\%$ (Gorokhovich *et al.*, 2006). The precision is less when measuring the absolute elevation in surfaces narrower than 180 m, as occurs in some path of the river channel and locally in terraces. In these cases the elevation data have been contrasted with field measurements using a conventional altimeter, based in atmospheric pressure. Although the absolute elevation value requires frequent calibration (according to atmospheric conditions), in our analysis we do not use the absolute elevation data, but the elevation difference between terrace surfaces and the current river. The altimeter accuracy when comparing the elevation of two surfaces is acceptable if measurements were done in a short time lapse, being ~ 1 m of uncertainty for each 10 m. Relative structural uplift has been calculated by comparing the relative elevation with respect to the current river at both sides of a tectonic flexure, assuming that the original depositional surface sloped at a gradient similar to today's stream. The dating of the fluvial surfaces allows the fluvial incision rates and relative uplift rates to be calculated.

4. Longitudinal river profiles and knickpoint analysis

4.1. Moulouya river

The longitudinal profile for the Moulouya river is not the typical concave shape of an equilibrium river, but has a series of knickpoints. The upper reach of the Moulouya river flows over alluvial deposits through a wide valley, presenting a surprisingly gentle gradient of 0.16° along its upper 50 km, after which there is an abrupt increase in slope (gradient $> 0.3^\circ$) for about 10 km defining a 80 m-high knickpoint (Fig. 2b). This is where the river flows over less erodible Paleozoic granitic bedrock. Downstream, the Moulouya river flows again over alluvial deposits and it returns to its gentle slope until it meets with the Asseghmir river. The Asseghmir river drains $\sim 1,350 \text{ km}^2$ of the northern flank of the High Atlas, representing a third of the total drainage area of the Moulouya river downstream of their confluence. The longitudinal profile of the Asseghmir river has a knickpoint of similar characteristics to those on the Moulouya river (Fig. 2a), but it is located in the northern flank of the High Atlas Mountains at an elevation $\sim 300 \text{ m}$ higher than in the Moulouya river. From the tributary junction, the Moulouya river flows east for almost 50 km across Jurassic limestone, granite and slate of the Aouli Massif with a steeper gradient of 0.38° until it reaches the Tamdafelt fold system (Figs. 1 and 2a). This steep increment of the slope defines a knickzone that is 300-400 m in height (Fig. 2b). The Enjil river joins the Moulouya downstream this knickzone, but the Enjil river also has a knickzone in its long profile, located near the confluence with the Moulouya river (Fig. 2a).

Downstream from the Tamdafelt fold system (Fig. 1), the Moulouya river flows along the Missouri sedimentary basin where its gradient becomes gentle again, averaging 0.14° for $> 150 \text{ km}$. A slight increase in the gradient occurs again at the boundary between the Missouri and Guercif basins, where the river flows over Jurassic dolomites, but the gradient becomes gentler in the Guercif basin, averaging 0.12° until the drainage basin outlet. Along the Missouri and Guercif basins, the Moulouya river receives waters from tributary streams that drain both the High Plateaus and the Middle Atlas (Jebel Bou Naceur), most notably the Za river.

4.2. Tributaries draining the High Plateaus to the Moulouya river

The western edge of the High Plateaus is drained by tributaries of the Moulouya river. These have significant knickzones along their lengths (shown as red reaches in Fig. 3). Figure 4a shows the long profiles of the Moulouya river and its tributaries all sharing the same distance to the Mediterranean outlet. All profiles have gentler slopes in their upper reaches (generally $<0.2^\circ$), with an abrupt increase in slope along their middle stretches, and progressively gentler slopes downstream. The gentle gradient of the upper segments suggests that little channel incision has occurred upstream of the knickpoints, and therefore these upper stretches can be interpreted as the gradient inherited from the Missouri basin paleosurface. In this case, the lateral correlation of these gentle gradients allows us to delineate a paleosurface reaching 500-550 m above the present Moulouya river (Fig. 4a). Figures 4b, 4c and 4d show the longitudinal profiles of three of tributaries of the Moulouya river. The knickpoints for the tributaries Fajane and Kaddou, draining the High Plateaus to the Missouri basin are 500 and 550 m high, respectively (Figs. 4b and 4c). The Za river is the main tributary of the Moulouya and it drains $\sim 20,000$ km² of the High Plateaus to the lower Guercif basin. The upper segment of the Za river flows for ~ 300 km and is inset into the Plio-Pleistocene fluvial deposits of the High Plateaus, that are locally entrenched to a depth of ~ 100 m, being the highest amounts close to the knickzone. The gradient of the upper reach is 0.15° , while downstream, the gradient increases to 0.33° for almost 80 km where the river crosses the eastern edge of the Guercif basin that is composed of Jurassic carbonates and has a knickzone with a height of 400-450 m (Fig. 4d). Given an estimate incision of ~ 100 m for the whole of the Guercif basin, deduced by the entrenchment of the Za river, the knickpoint height should be 500-550 m.

4.3. Tributaries draining the Jebel Bou Naceur to the Moulouya river

The Chegg Ard, El Mansoor, El Berd and Timrhout rivers draining the southeastern Jebel Bou Naceur flow into the Missouri and Guercif basins (Fig. 3). The Chegg Ard is the main river draining the southern part of the Jebel Bou Naceur into the Missouri basin and has a catchment area of ~ 240 km² in the mountains. The longitudinal profile of the Chegg Ard river has an impressive knickpoint 1000 m-high (Fig. 5a), which is located at approximately the junction between the Toarcian marls and the overlying Bathonian-Callovian Bou Rached Sandstone of Charroud (2002). The upstream stretch of the Chegg

Ard river flows for ~10 km in a wide valley (Fig. 5b), where the channel is slightly entrenched and has a gradient of 1.3°. Downstream, the channel gradient abruptly increases to 3.1°. In this 13 km-long stretch, the channel is deeply entrenched and its tributaries exhibit evidence of recent incision. From the knickpoint to the confluence in the Moulouya river, the Chegg Ard river has an average gradient of 0.9°.

Tributary streams that flow along the structural grain of the Middle Atlas drain the eastern edge of the Jebel Bou Naceur. These tributaries converge downstream to become the Melloulou river (Fig. 3). The Melloulou river joins the Moulouya river in the middle of the Guercif basin. Tributaries of the Melloulou river include the El Mansoor, El Berd and Timrhout rivers, which have large knickpoints in their mountainous stretches with heights of 700-800 m (Figs. 5c and 5d). The channel of the Timrhout river has been blocked by a rock landslide to form a lake, Gualta Tamda (Fig. 5e). The location of the landslide coincides with the upper segment of an 800 m-high knickpoint, suggesting that the landslide may have been partially triggered by rapid fluvial incision.

5. Description of Quaternary fluvial surfaces in the lower Chegg Ard valley

Alluvial fan and fluvial surfaces along the Chegg Ard, the main river draining the Jebel Bou Naceur to the Missouri basin, were selected for dating because they preserve a good record of fluvial deposits and exhibit signs of recent deformation relating to folds associated with the southern Middle Atlas thrust front (Fig. 6) (Laville *et al.*, 2007; Delcaillau *et al.*, 2007). Four sets of fluvial deposits and abandoned alluvial fan surfaces were mapped along the Chegg Ard valley, which we name T1 (oldest) to T4 (youngest) (Figs. 6 and 7).

The T1 is an extensive alluvial fan surface which has a radial length of ~12 km with its apex located near the mountain front, at the boundary between the Middle Atlas Mesozoic carbonate rocks and the Tertiary clastic deposits of the Missouri basin. This alluvial fan surface is entrenched by the Chegg Ard channel to a depth of 135-185 m. The T1 surface is composed of fanlomerate that is 1-5 m thick, and overlies conglomerates of the Tertiary Bou Irhardaiene Formation. The T1 fanlomerate and the Bou Irhardaiene

Formation are conformable and have similar sedimentological characteristics, locally making difficult to distinguish between the two units. The contact between them, however, is easy to recognize in deformed areas, because there is a slight angular unconformity between them. The T1 deposit is composed of cobbles and boulders that become smaller downstream. Locally, in the upper areas of the abandoned alluvial fan, old longitudinal bars are present composed of >50 cm-diameter imbricated boulders, suggestive of a highly energetic depositional environment. The clasts comprise mainly carbonate rocks. The T1 surface has well-developed pedogenic carbonate cement (Stage V of Gile *et al.*, 1981). The alluvial fan is almost completely eroded southward from the frontal monocline fold (FMF; Fig. 6). Surface T1 is rare south of the FMF, being restricted to small remnants in the forelimb of the FMF. Stratified conglomerates abutting the forelimb of the frontal monocline fold, unconformable on the Bou Irhardaiene Formation conglomerates, may be the sole remnants of T1 in the foreland of the FMF. The presence of embedded deposits suggests a relative base level drop, and we assume that remnants of T1 had to be formed above the surface T2, at least 35 m above the current level.

The abandoned fluvial and alluvial surface T2 is present in three locations along the Chegg Ard valley (Fig. 6b). The main exposure is present to the south of the FMF, where it forms a large lobe of an alluvial fan that extends for 14 km until it reaches the Moulouya river, which we call T2b. Other remnants are present as river terraces in the cores of the FMF and the Beni Aïoun anticline, which we call T2c and T2a, respectively (Figs. 6a, 7 and 7a). The T2 deposits have the same general characteristics as T1, but the average size of the clasts is smaller, rarely reaching > 20 cm in diameter. These surfaces usually have moderate pedogenic carbonate development (carbonate morphology stage III-IV of Gile *et al.*, 1981). The T3 and T4 deposits are well preserved south of the FMF. Both show similar features to T2, but the carbonate cement is less developed. T3 is composed of decimeter-size clasts, some of them reaching 30 cm in diameter, whereas the T4 has smaller clasts (rarely reaching 15 cm in diameter), which in places are imbricated and stratified.

6. ¹⁰Be Terrestrial cosmogenic nuclide results

6.1. Erosion rate estimates using surface clasts

TCN concentrations can be used to estimate erosion rates (erosional equilibrium; Lal, 1991). For estimating steady-state erosion rates, samples with higher TCN concentrations provide lower limits on erosion rates. We use the ^{10}Be concentrations in the clasts for samples on the T1 surface (except M918, which was significantly younger than the other ages) to estimate the erosion rate using the methods of Lal (1991). This provides a minimum erosion-rate estimate because we preferentially selected clasts that appeared more resistant to erosion, most still preserving their well-rounded fluvial shapes and an absence of notable weathering features such as exfoliated surfaces, pitting, or granular disintegration. Moreover, the surface of the T1 is strongly cemented, increasing its resistance to erosion. We use the ten oldest ages of surface clasts to calculate an erosion rate. This gives a mean erosion rate of $1.4 \pm 0.2 \text{ m Ma}^{-1}$, which is in good agreement with those for other climatically similar settings (Matmon *et al.*, 2009; Portenga and Bierman, 2011) as discussed in Arboleya *et al.* (2008), in their study and terrace dating in the proximal Ouarzazate basin.

6.2. Ages of surfaces in the Chegg Ard Valley

Sampled boulders may retain a signal of prior exposure with inherited TCNs from their previous location, sometimes referred to as ‘derived’, which result in ages that are older than the surface being dated (Anderson *et al.*, 1996; Hancock *et al.*, 1999). Intense weathering or exhumation of clasts may result in lower concentrations of TCNs, which will underestimate the age of the surface. Collecting multiple samples from each terrace and looking for potential outliers, that is, exposure ages that fall significantly outside the mean value ($>2 \sigma$) of all the ages obtained for a given landform, can help identify the problem of derived and/or weathered/exhumed boulders. We use the erosion rates estimates based on the oldest ten ages for surface clasts (as described in the previous section) as a test to assess the likely effects of erosion on the samples used to define the ages of the surfaces. For samples having an erosion rate of 1.4 m Ma^{-1} , a calculated age of 10 ka would underestimate the true age by a $\sim 1\%$, an age of 50 ka by $\sim 5\%$, an age of 100 ka by $\sim 10\%$, and an age of 300 ka by $\sim 50\%$. Given the uncertainties in defining the erosion rate, we plot all our ages with zero erosion, but also present them in Table 1 for an erosion rate of 1.4 m Ma^{-1} , which places an upper limit on the possible ages when considering erosion in this region.

Surface T1 has been dated using 11 samples from two different localities (T1a and T1b in Fig. 6), and yields ages that range from 321 to 528 ka (Fig. 8), with a mean age of 411 ± 55 ka (uncertainty = 1σ). The sampled clasts of sandstone and phyllite were carefully selected from the surface, mainly composed of carbonate rocks. Since the sampled clasts were well rounded, retaining their original shape, we argue that they have not undergone significant weathering. Twelve samples were dated on T2 surface at two different localities (T2a and T2b in Figures 6 and 7a), yielding ages of between 20 and 327 ka (Fig. 8). Samples M926 (327.8 ± 33.8 ka) and M927 (105.1 ± 10.0 ka) are much older than the other samples, being $>2 \sigma$ older than the mean age for the rest of the population. The presence of conglomerate clasts at locality T2b, reworked from T1 or from the Bou Irhardaiene Formation, supports the view that M926 and M927 have been derived from the older surface. Omitting the ages for M926 and M927, the T2 surface has a mean age 52 ± 20 ka (uncertainty = 1σ). Two other samples, M929 and M932, fall outside the mean value ($>2 \sigma$) with ages of 20.4 ± 10.0 ka and 22.0 ± 2.6 ka. We recognize that these younger age samples might have been exhumed, although we cannot prove this assumption. Omitting the ages of M926, M927, M929 and M932, the T2 surface has a mean age 62.6 ± 14.1 ka (uncertainty = 1σ). In the following we will use the older mean value for the age of T2 (62 ± 14 ka).

6.3. Tectonic uplift and incision rates of surfaces in the Chegg Ard Valley

The dated T1 and T2 surfaces are incised by the Chegg Ard river in different places along the Chegg Ard Valley, where incision can be measured in both the tectonically uplifted area of the basin and the central Missouri basin. The FMF and Beni Aioun anticline (Fig. 6) have deformed the upper segments of terraces T1 and T2 with respect their lower segments. The FMF is the frontal-most structure and is located ~ 12 km from the Middle Atlas mountain front, trending SW-NE and verging SE, with an almost horizontal backlimb and a subvertical forelimb, whereas the Beni Aioun anticline (BAA in Fig. 6) is a gentle anticline located between the mountain front and the FMF.

Immediately northwards of the FMF, in the tectonically uplifted fold limb, the T1a surface is 133 ± 3 m above the current river (Fig. 9). Terrace T1 is also tilted by the Beni Aioun anticline and reaches 182 ± 5 m above the current river near the mountain front (Fig. 9).

Thus, the incision rates measured from T1 in the tectonically uplifted area range from 0.32 ± 0.04 to 0.44 ± 0.06 mm a⁻¹ (Fig. 9). The difference between these rates is ~ 0.1 mm a⁻¹, and is likely attributed to the relative uplift generated by the Beni Aioun anticline.

Surface T2 is not continuously preserved along the Chegg Ard valley and is very little deformed, but its elevation with respect the current river significantly varies along the valley. T2 is present in the cores of the FMF and the Beni Aioun anticline, being at ~ 51 to 55 m above the contemporary river, respectively (T2c and T2a in Figs. 6b and 7a; Fig.9). T2 also forms the alluvial fan located at the foreland of the FMF, being incised by $\sim 16\pm 3$ m in the distal reaches increasing to 32 ± 3 m in its upper reaches (T2b in Figs. 6b and 7a; Fig. 9). Such a wide range of incision values, with higher incision in the apex and lower incision in distal parts of the fan, is mostly due to the difference in gradient between the steeper slope of the incised alluvial fan and the gentler slope of the contemporary river. Using the surface age of 62 ± 14 ka for T2, we calculate incision rates that range from 0.28 ± 0.12 mm a⁻¹ in the distal reaches of the alluvial fan surface T2b to 0.55 ± 0.17 mm a⁻¹ in the proximal region (fan apex) of surface T2b (Fig. 9). The T2c, located in the core of the FMF at 51 ± 3 m (Fig. 9), is ~ 19 m more elevated with respect to the current river than the proximal parts of the surface T2b, which is located at an elevation of 32 ± 3 m above the channel, only 500 m downstream (Fig. 9). This difference in elevation corresponds to relative uplift by the FMF since the abandonment of T2, which would be at an average rate of ~ 0.3 - 0.4 mm a⁻¹. Such a rate is comparable to those recorded for the past 250 ka in the deformed terraces of the proximal Ouarzazate basin, in the foreland of the High Atlas (Pastor *et al.*, 2012).

The incision rate calculated for the terrace T1 at the backlimb of the FMF is 0.32 ± 0.04 mm a⁻¹, which is significantly lower than that obtained from the T2c surface which is 0.93 ± 0.26 mm a⁻¹ or from T2a that is 0.88 ± 0.25 mm a⁻¹ (Fig. 9). We suggest that the more recent rates (calculated from T2) are probably overestimated because of the terrace formation cycle incision/aggradation has not been completed (aggradation of the newest riverbed terrace), as Arboleya *et al.* (2008) documented in the Ouarzazate basin. Therefore, the longer-term incision rates are likely more representative of the basin incision rate, whereas more recent rates could result significantly higher due to climatic factors.

7. Discussion

7.1. Knickpoints, uplift and erosion in the Moulouya drainage basin

The analysis of longitudinal river profiles reveals the systematic presence of large knickpoints or knickzones in the Moulouya river and its main tributaries. The formation and upstream retreat of knickpoints is typically understood as the dominant mode of channel adjustment in response to either regional or local perturbations due to one or more of the following: regional uplift (e.g., Burbank and Anderson, 2001; Lavé and Avouac, 2001; Wobus *et al.*, 2006; Quezada *et al.*, 2010); localized structural uplift (e.g., Burbank *et al.*, 1996); regional base level drop (e.g., Begin *et al.*, 1981; Snyder *et al.*, 2002; Bishop *et al.*, 2005; Crosby and Whipple, 2006); local base level fall directly caused by a river piracy (e.g., García, 2006); and/or differential erosion caused by a lithological contrast (e.g., Goldrick and Bishop, 2007). Other causes may be associated with inherited relief features due to glacial erosion and/or landsliding (e.g., Benda and Dunne, 1997; Korup *et al.*, 2006; Lancaster and Grant, 2006). Knickpoints in the upper Moulouya drainage network, near the Middle Atlas front, were interpreted by Laville *et al.* (2007) and Delcaillau *et al.* (2008) as due solely to recent thrust deformation, without discussing the potential role of regional uplift and base level drop on knickpoint formation. Similarly, in the southern mountain front of the High Atlas, Boulton *et al.* (2014) interpreted existing knickpoints as entirely related to active faults.

The knickpoints of the Missouri and Guercif basins are situated on tributaries draining both sides of the Moulouya river, from the stable High Plateaus and the active Middle Atlas, and must be explained by a regional-scale process. This regional-scale process is most likely the adaptation of the fluvial network to the mantle-driven, long-wavelength uplift. This uplift remains active in the region (Barbero *et al.*, 2011; Barcos *et al.*, 2014) and has produced a maximum surface uplift of ~ 1000 m at a rate ranging from 0.17 to 0.22 mm.a⁻¹ since at least the earliest Pliocene (Babault *et al.*, 2008). The Missouri basin was still accumulating sediments (Bou Irhardaiene Formation) at least until the early Pliocene, after the mantle-related uplift started. The aperture of the basin probably happened when the basin surface was raised at a significant elevation and had accumulated potential energy with respect to the base level of the capturing river. The capture of an endorheic basin likely triggers faster erosion rates during the first stages of erosion, which in the study case may have caused the development of a knickpoint that

propagated upwards along the entire fluvial network, which now can be identified at the lithological contrasts between the Neogene basin fill and the Jurassic carbonate bedrock along the basin margins. There, headward propagation become slower due to the reduction of incision capacity related to more resistant bedrock and to the smaller drainage area at the upper segments of rivers.

The analysis of the river long profiles shows that the height of the knickpoints differ in the High Plateaus margin from the Middle Atlas thrust front, where knickpoints present larger vertical drop in channel elevation downstream from the knickpoint. The knickpoints in rivers draining the eastern margin of the Missouri basin (adjacent to the High Plateaus), where there are no active tectonic structures, show 500-550 m of projected heights at the junction with the Moulouya river (Fig. 4). This is consistent with the lacustrine deposits preserved in the eastern margin of the Missouri basin at ~550 m above the present Moulouya river (labeled Q6 on the 1/100,000 geological map of Hassi el Ahmar and attributed to the Villafranchian -indetermined upper Pliocene; Choubert, 1964), which we interpret as the maximum elevation reached by the basin fill before it started to erode.

The long profile of the Moulouya river has a knickzone with a vertical drop of 300-400 m located at the boundary between the Arhbalou and Missouri basins. Laville *et al.* (2007) attribute such knickzone to active deformation in the Tamdafelt fold system, located just at the base of the knickzone. However, the knickzone as a whole is coincident with the lithological contrast between the easily erodible sediments of the Missouri basin and the Jurassic carbonates and Paleozoic basement rocks of the Aouli Massif. Alternatively, we propose that the knickzone is related to the uplift that affected the entire drainage basin, which caused the knickpoint to propagate upstream until the river lost its erosive capacity at the location of the contrasting lithologies. The knickzone within the Moulouya river is 150-250 m lower than the ones measured in its tributaries draining the High Plateaus. This is probably because the Arhbalou basin (upstream of the Moulouya's longitudinal profile knickzone) has already suffered erosion, as suggested by the fluvial incision (locally reaching 150 m) affecting alluvial deposits in the piedmonts of the High and Middle Atlas. As a testament of this process, the Gara of Midelt is a butte composed by Neogene sediments that is preserved in the middle Arhbalou basin, reaching more than

100 m above the current surface, which provides a minimum estimate of the elevation of the basin fill.

7.2. Thrust uplift of the Jebel Bou Naceur

The main rivers draining the Jebel Bou Naceur to the Missouri and Guercif basins have knickzones with higher difference in elevation than those measured in tributaries draining the High Plateaus. Laville *et al.* (2007) and Delcaillau *et al.* (2007) analyzed Quaternary deposits and knickpoints along major drainages of the southern flank of the Middle Atlas, and interpreted the modern landforms as responding to recent thrust tectonic deformation, although they did not quantify rates of deformation or discuss the potential role of regional uplift. The impressive 1000 m-high knickzone of the Chegg Ard river (Fig. 5a) was interpreted exclusively as a result of recent out-of-sequence thrusting by these authors.

The El Mansoor, El Berd and Timrhout tributaries drain the eastern edge of the Jebel Bou Naceur to the Guercif basin (Fig. 3) and have knickzones with heights of 700-800 m (Figs. 5c and 5d). We propose that, as happens in tributaries draining the High Plateaus, 500-550 m of the total height of these knickzones is the result of the regional-scale uplift, whereas the remaining 450-500 m in the central Southern Middle Atlas frontal zone (Fig. 10), and 200-300 m in the eastern edge of the Jebel Bou Naceur, can be explained by the localized (thrust-related) uplift of the Middle Atlas in its frontal structures. In the Chegg Ard valley, signs of tectonic deformation in Quaternary alluvial deposits attest to the active structures emerging within the Missouri basin. Delcaillau *et al.* (2007) proposed small knickpoints within the Missouri basin and relate them to active structures. We argue that knickpoint preservation is rare within the basin where streams flow over easily erodible sediments. As occurs with the progressive long-wavelength uplift, the thrust-related knickpoints retreat upstream until they reach more resistant rock types, for example, at the boundary between Neogene basin fills and Mesozoic carbonate rocks. Such resistant lithologies become more difficult for the streams to erode, and therefore, knickpoints become knickzones that remain at the lithological boundary for some time, progressively increasing in height. Hence, neither the current location nor the elevation

of knickzones along the Moulouya fluvial network can be simply related to the active thrust deformation as suggested by Delcaillau *et al.* (2007).

7.3. Recent rates of regional (mantle-driven) and local (thrust-related) uplift

Our TCN dating of surfaces T1 and T2 allows us to calculate incision rates at different points along the Chegg Ard valley. Moreover, the different surface ages (T2: 62 ± 14 ka and T1: 411 ± 55 ka) allow us to examine incision rates over different time spans, particularly for the area affected by the uplift generated by the FMF. Incision rates measured in the upper Chegg Ard valley must result from the mantle-driven uplift plus the structural uplift produced by the frontal structures of the Middle Atlas, the FMF and the Beni Aioun anticline, deforming both the T1 and T2 surfaces. On the other hand, we argue that incision rates calculated for the lower reach of the Chegg Ard river, ahead of the frontal-most tectonic structure within the Missouri basin, are valid for the Moulouya river nearby, which forms the base level for the Middle Atlas tributaries. These rates may be taken as a proxy for the recent uplift rates related to dynamic topography within the Moulouya drainage basin, understood as large-scale, regional uplift due to buoyancy changes in the mantle not directly related to tectonic shortening of the crust (e.g., Coblenz and Karlstrom, 2011; Nereson *et al.*, 2013 for terminology).

Average regional surface uplift rates since the latest Miocene or earliest Pliocene were measured in the northern Middle Atlas by Babault *et al.* (2008) at ~ 0.2 mm a⁻¹, on the basis of elevated Messinian marine deposits, scarcely eroded and lying at 1200 m asl in the Skoura area, only 65 km WNW of our study area. The marine Messinian dated by Krijgsman and Langereis (2000) in the center of the Guercif basin is significantly lower, at 450-650 m asl, and the surface uplift rate in that basin is of ~ 0.1 mm a⁻¹. Hence, we retain the value of 0.1-0.2 mm.a⁻¹ based on messinian shallow marine sediments for the average background rock uplift of the study area during the late Pleistocene. The incision rate of 0.28 ± 0.12 mm a⁻¹ at the distal part of T2b in the Missouri basin is of the same order of magnitude, or slightly greater, than the average surface uplift since the latest Miocene or earliest Pliocene in the Middle Atlas (Babault *et al.*, 2008). We discussed above that T2-based rates may be slight overestimations.

We suggest that the incision rate in the lower reach of the Chegg Ard river in the last ~411 ka is keeping pace with the rising dynamic topography at a rate of ~0.1-0.2 mm a⁻¹. Under this assumption, the fluvial incision rate calculated at T1c near the Jebel Bou Naceur mountain front at 0.44±0.06 mm a⁻¹ (Fig. 9) can be attributed to ~0.1-0.2 mm a⁻¹ of regional uplift plus ~0.3 mm a⁻¹ of thrust-related uplift in the basin folds.

The combination of the geomorphic analysis of longitudinal river profiles and the incision rates presented above provide inferences about the recent tectonic and erosional history of the Missouri basin. We showed that the Chegg Ard longitudinal river profile exhibits a knickpoint with a height of 1,000 m, 500-550 m of which might be explained by mantle-driven (regional) uplift and the remaining 450-500 m by upthrusting of the Jebel Bou Naceur (Fig. 10). However, our geochronological data suggests that, since the Middle Pleistocene, the rate of local structural uplift has been greater than that of the regional uplift. Our calculations imply a local structural uplift rate of ~0.3 mm a⁻¹ since the Middle Pleistocene within the Missouri basin close to the mountain front in association with the two frontal structures. We cannot discard the possibility that other active structures are present in the mountain area, but as a first approximation, we retain the minimum value of 0.3 mm a⁻¹, and at such rate, the 450-500 m height of the knickzone related to thrust activity would have been produced in 1.2-1.5 Ma.

The capture of the basin developed a knickpoint that propagated upwards along the entire fluvial network, which today can be identified at the lithological contrasts along the basin margins. Favoring this view, terrace T1 is the older of the Pleistocene deposits and is characterized by larger clast sizes that suggest a very high-energy transportational/depositional setting, which allow relating its formation to a very strong perturbation occurred in the Chegg Ard fluvial system, as probably was the accumulation of an important knickpoint height at the mountain front. The increment of the knickpoint relief near the mountain front involves an abrupt steepening of the hillslopes, and therefore, an increased supply of coarse sediments. The thick alluvial deposits reported by Bouazza *et al.* (2009) in the outlet of two gorges incised by the Za and Moulouya rivers, in Beni Snassen and the Horts Chain may have had a similar origin. Alternatively, the formation of T2 could be related to changes in climate, as suggested by Arboleya *et al.* (2008) for the extensive Quaternary fanglomerates of similar age in the Ouarzazate basin or due to tectonic changes such as pulses in the tectonic activity of the FMF as suggested by Delcaillau *et al.* (2008).

8. Conclusions

Geomorphic analysis of the Moulouya drainage network within the Missouri basin and adjacent highlands (Middle Atlas and High Plateaus) reveals the existence of knickpoints or knickzones along most streams. The knickpoints are located in the rivers draining the tectonically active margin of the Middle Atlas as well as in those draining the relatively tectonically quiescent High Plateaus. The systematic presence of knickpoints attests to the adjustment of the fluvial network to regional (long-wavelength) surface uplift of mantle origin (dynamic topography), which resulted in the Missouri basin changing from dominantly aggradational to erosional in the late Pliocene or early Quaternary. Geomorphic evidence shows that the knickpoints related to the regional uplift propagated upstream along the Moulouya river and its tributaries. The height of the knickpoints along the rivers draining the undeformed (High Plateaus) margin indicates that 500-550 m of sediments have been eroded in the central parts of the Neogene Missouri and Guercif basins. In contrast, rivers draining the tectonically active margin of the Middle Atlas (Jebel Bou Naceur) have knickpoints that are 800-1000 m high. From the undeformed margin it can be inferred that 500-550 m of this height might be explained by regional dynamic uplift, whereas the remaining 450-500 m in the central part of the southern Middle Atlas Front and the 200-300 m in the northeastern edge of the Middle Atlas are related to thrust uplift of the Jebel Bou Naceur (Fig. 10).

Two Quaternary river terraces in the Chegg Ard valley date to 62 ± 14 ka and 411 ± 55 ka. These river terraces allow rates of incision with respect to the undeformed surfaces of the Missouri basin produced by the leading structures of the Middle Atlas emerging within the basin, and of the background incision rate due to mantle-sourced regional uplift since the Middle Pleistocene to be estimated. The rate of structural uplift in the system of foreland folds is estimated to be $\sim 0.3 \text{ mm a}^{-1}$, whereas the background incision rate is $\sim 0.1\text{-}0.2 \text{ mm a}^{-1}$ in the central part of the Missouri basin. The accumulation of the voluminous T1 deposit, where huge boulder forming imbricated bars attest for a very high energetic depositional environment, is likely due to the moment in what the capture-

related knickpoint reached the mountain front. On the other hand, the formation of T2 is probably related to changes in climate or a local tectonic pulse in the front.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by Spanish projects CGL2010-15416, CGL2007-66431-CO2-01 (TOPOMED), and Consolider-Ingenio2010 CSD2006-00041 (TOPOIBERIA). Mohammed Charroud is thanked for early guidance to the field area. The comments by J.V. Pérez-Peña and an anonymous reviewer helped substantially to improve the original manuscript.

References

- Anderson, R.S., Repka, J.L., Dick, G.S., 1996. Explicit treatment of inheritance in dating depositional surfaces using in situ ^{10}Be and ^{26}Al . *Geology* 24, 47–51.
- Avouac, J.-P., Peltzer, G., 1993. Active Tectonics in Southern Xinjiang, China: Analysis of Terrace Riser and Normal Fault Scarp Degradation Along the Hotan-Qira Fault System. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 98 (B12), 21773-21807.
- Arboleya, M.L., Teixell, A., Charroud, M., Julivert, M., 2004. A structural transect through the High and Middle Atlas of Morocco. *Journal of African Earth Sciences* 39, 319–327.
- Arboleya, M.-L., Babault, J., Owen, L.A., Teixell, A., Finkel, R.C., 2008. Timing and nature of fluvial incision in the Ouarzazate foreland basin, Morocco. *Journal of the Geological Society, London* 165, 1059-1073.
- Ayarza, P., Carbonell, R., Teixell, A., Palomeras, I., Martí, D., Kchikach, M., Levander, A., Gallart, J., Arboleya, M.L., Alcalde, J., Fernández, M., Charroud, M., Amrhar, M., 2014. Crustal thickness and velocity structure across the Moroccan Atlas from long offset wide-angle reflection seismic data: The SIMA experiment. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems* 15, 1698-1717.
- Babault, J., Teixell, A., Arboleya, M.L., Charroud, M., 2008. A Late Cenozoic age for long-wavelength surface uplift of the Atlas Mountains of Morocco. *Terra Nova* 20, 102–107.
- Balco, G., Stone, J.O., Lifton, N.A., Dunai T.J., 2008. A complete and easily accessible means of calculating surface exposure ages or erosion rates from ^{10}Be and ^{26}Al measurements. *Quaternary Geochronology* 8, 174-195.
- Barbero, L., Jabaloy, A., Gómez-Ortiz, D., Pérez-Peña, J.V., Rodríguez-Peces, M.J., Tejero, R., Estupiñán, J., Azdimousa, A., Vázquez, M., Asebriy, L., 2011. Evidence for surface uplift of the Atlas Mountains and the surrounding peripheral plateaux: Combining apatite fission track results and geomorphic indicators in the Western Moroccan Meseta (Coastal Variscan Paleozoic Basement). *Tectonophysics* 502, 90-104.

- Barcos, L., Jabaloy, A., Azdimousa, A., Asebriy, L., Gómez-Ortiz, D., Rodríguez-Peces, M.J., Tejero, R., Pérez-Peña, J.V., 2014. Study of relief changes related to active doming in the eastern Moroccan Rif (Morocco) using geomorphological indices. *Journal of African Earth Sciences* 100: 493-509.
- Barke, R., Lamb, S., 2006. Late Cenozoic uplift of the Eastern Cordillera, Bolivian Andes. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 249, 350-367.
- Beauchamp, W., Barazangi, M., Demnati, A., El Alji, M., 1996. Intracontinental Rifting and Inversion: Missouri Basin and Atlas Mountains, Morocco. *AAPG Bulletin* 80, 1459-1482.
- Begin, Z.e.B., Meyer, D.F., Schumm, S.A., 1981. Development of longitudinal profiles of alluvial channels in response to base-level lowering. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 6, 49-68.
- Benda, L., Dunne, T., 1997. Stochastic forcing of sediment routing and storage in channel networks. *Water Resources Research* 33, 2865-2880.
- Bernini, M., Boccaletti, M., Gelatti, R., Moratti, G., Papani, G., El Mokhtari, J., 1999. Tectonics and sedimentation in the Taza-Guercif basin, northern Morocco: implications for the Neogene evolution of the Rif-Middle Atlas orogenic system. *Journal of Petroleum Geology* 22, 115-128.
- Bernini, M., Boccaletti, M., Moratti, G., Papani, G., 2000. Structural development of the Taza-Guercif Basin as a constraint for the Middle Atlas Shear Zone tectonic evolution. *Marine and Petroleum Geology* 17, 391-408.
- Bishop, P., 2007. Long-term landscape evolution: linking tectonics and surface processes. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 32, 329-365.
- Bishop, P., Hoey, T.B., Jansen, J.D., Artza, I.L., 2005. Knickpoint recession rate and catchment area: the case of uplifted rivers in Eastern Scotland. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 30, 767-778.
- Bouazza, A., AïtBrahim, L., Dugué, O., Laville, E., Delcaillau, B., Cattaneo, G., Charroud, M., de Luca, P., 2009. Changements Sédimentaires dans les Bassins Néogènes de Taourirt et Guercif (Maroc Oriental): Recherche de l'épisode d'érosion Messinienne. *European Journal of Scientific Research* 28, 317-327.
- Boulton, S.J., Stokes, M., Mather, A.E., 2014. Transient fluvial incision as an indicator of active faulting and Plio-Quaternary uplift of the Moroccan High Atlas. *Tectonophysics* 633, 16-33
- Burbank, D.W., Leland, J., Fielding, E., Anderson, R.S., Brozovic, N., Reid, M.R., Duncan, C., 1996. Bedrock incision, rock uplift and threshold hillslopes in the northwestern Himalaya. *Nature* 379, 505-510.
- Burbank, D.W., Anderson, R.S., 2001. *Tectonic Geomorphology*. Blackwell Science, Malden, USA, 274 pp.

- Charroud, A., 2002. Evolution géodynamique des hauts plateaux (Maroc) et de leurs bordures du Mésozoïque au Cénozoïque. Thesis 3^e Cycle, Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah, Fes, 314 pp.
- Choubert, M.G., 1964. Carte géologique du Maroc, sheet NI-30-IX-2: Hassi el Ahmar. Service Géologique du Maroc, Notes et Mémoires. Ministère de l'Énergie et des Mines, Direction de la Géologie, Rabat.
- Coblentz, D., Karlstrom, K.E., 2011. Tectonic geomorphometrics of the western United States: Speculations on the surface expression of upper mantle processes. *Geochemistry Geophysics Geosystems* 12, Q11002, doi:10.1029/2011GC003579.
- Delcaillau, B., Laville, E., Carozza, J.-M., Dugué, O., Charroud, M., Amrhar, M., 2007. Morphotectonic evolution of the Jebel Bou Naceur in the South Middle Atlas Fault Zone (Morocco). *Comptes Rendus Geoscience* 339, 553-561.
- Dutour, A., 1983. Etude géomorphologique de la partie occidentale de la Haute Moulouya (Maroc). Thesis 3^e Cycle Thesis, Poitiers, 361 pp.
- Ellouz, N., Patriat, M., Gaulier, J.-M., Bouatmani, R., Sabounji, S., 2003. From rifting to Alpine inversion: Mesozoic and Cenozoic subsidence history of some Moroccan basins. *Sedimentary Geology* 156, 185–212.
- Fuller, J., Fernández, M., Afonso, J.C., Vergés, J., Zeyen, H., 2010. The structure and evolution of the lithosphere–asthenosphere boundary beneath the Atlantic–Mediterranean Transition Region. *Lithos* 120, 74-95.
- Gile, L.H., Hawley, J.W., Grossman, R.B., 1981. Soils and geomorphology in the Basin and Range area of southern New Mexico – Guidebook to the Desert Project. New Mexico Bureau of Mines and Mineral Resources, Memoir, 39, 222 pp.
- Goldrick, G., Bishop, P., 2007. Regional analysis of bedrock stream long profiles: evaluation of Hack's SL form, and formulation and assessment of an alternative (the DS form). *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 32, 649-671.
- Gomez, F., Allmendinger, R., Barazangi, M., Er-Raji, A., Dahmani, M., 1998. Crustal shortening and vertical strain partitioning in the Middle Atlas mountains of Morocco. *Tectonics* 17, 520–533.
- Gomez F., Barazangi M., Bensaïd M., 1996. Active tectonism in the intracontinental Middle Atlas mountains of Morocco: synchronous crustal shortening and extension. *Journal of Geological Society, London* 153, 389–402.
- Gomez, F., Barazangi, M., Demnati, A., 2000. Structure and Evolution of the Neogene Guercif Basin at the Junction of the Middle Atlas Mountains and the Rif Thrust Belt, Morocco. *AAPG Bulletin* 84, 1340-1364.

- Hack, J.T. (1957). Studies of longitudinal stream profiles in Virginia and Maryland. United States Geological Survey Professional Paper 294(B), 45-94.
- Hancock, G.S., Anderson, R.S., Chadwick, O.A., Finkel, R.C., 1999. Dating fluvial terraces with ^{10}Be and ^{26}Al profiles: application to the Wind River, Wyoming. *Geomorphology* 27, 41–60
- Hoke, G.D., Isacks, B.L., Jordan, T.E., Blanco, N., Tomlinson, A.J., Ramezani, J., 2007. Geomorphic evidence for post-10 Ma uplift of the western flank of the central Andes. *Tectonics* 26, doi: 10.1029/2006TC002082.
- Korup, O., 2006. Rock-slope failure and the river long profile. *Geology* 34, 45-48.
- Krijgsman, W., Langereis, C.G., 2000. Magnetostratigraphy of the Zobzit and Koudiat Zarga sections (Taza-Guercif Basin, Morocco); implications for the evolution of the Rifian Corridor. *Marine and Petroleum Geology* 17, 359-371.
- Lal, D., 1991. Cosmic ray labeling of erosion surfaces: in situ nuclide production rates and erosion models. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 104, 429–439.
- Lancaster, S.T., Grant, G.E., 2006. Debris dams and the relief of headwater streams. *Geomorphology* 82, 84-97.
- Lavé, J., Avouac, J.P., 2001. Fluvial incision and tectonic uplift across the Himalayas of central Nepal. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 106, 26561-26591.
- Laville, E., Delcaillau, B., Charroud, M., Dugué, O., AitBrahim, L., Cattaneo, G., Deluca, P., Bouazza, A., 2007. The Plio-Pleistocene evolution of the Southern Middle Atlas Fault Zone (SMAFZ) front of Morocco. *International Journal of Earth Sciences* 96, 497-515.
- Matmon, A., Simhai, O., Amit, R., Haviv, I., Porat, N., McDonald, E., Benedetti, L., Finkel, R., 2009. Desert pavement-coated surfaces in extreme desert presents the longest-lived landforms on Earth. *Geol. Soc. America Bulletin* 121, 688-697.
- Melhaoui, M., Sbai, A., 2008. Expertise nationale en socio économie et développement local appliquée à la gestion intégrée des zones côtières : Cas de la zone Saïdia - Moulouya - Cap de l'eau. Projet SMAP III Moulouya. Rapport final. Secrétariat d'Etat auprès du Ministère de l'Energie, des Mines de l'Eau et de l'Environnement, chargé de l'Eau et de l'Environnement. Département de l'Environnement, 204 pp.
- Miller, M.S., Becker, T.W., 2014. Reactivated lithospheric-scale discontinuities localize dynamic uplift of the Moroccan Atlas Mountains. *Geology* 42, 35-38.
- Nereson, A., Stroud, J., Karlstrom, K., Heizler, M., McIntosh, W., 2013. Dynamic topography of the western Great Plains: Geomorphic and $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ evidence for mantle-driven uplift associated with the Jemez lineament of NE New Mexico and SE Colorado. *Geosphere* 9, 521-545.

- Palomeras, I., Thurner, S., Levander, A., Liu, K., Villasenor, A., Carbonell, R., Harnafi, M., 2014. Finite-frequency Rayleigh wave tomography of the western Mediterranean: Mapping its lithospheric structure. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems* 15, 140-160.
- Pastor, A., Teixell, A., Arboleya, M.L., 2012. Rates of Quaternary deformation in the Ouarzazate Basin (Southern Atlas Front, Morocco). *Annals of Geophysics* 55, 1003-1016.
- Paul, J., Roberts, G. y White, N., 2014. The african landscape through space and time. *Tectonics* 33, 898-935.
- Portenga, E.W., Bierman, P.R., 2011. Understanding Earth's eroding surface with ^{10}Be . *Geology Today* 21, 4-10.
- Quezada, J., Cerda, J.L., Jensen, A., 2010. Efectos de la tectónica y el clima en la configuración morfológica del relieve costero del norte de Chile. *Andean Geology* 37, 78-109.
- Sani, F., Zizi, M., Bally, A.W., 2000. The Neogene-Quaternary evolution of the Guercif Basin (Morocco) reconstructed from seismic line interpretation. *Marine and Petroleum Geology* 17, 343-357.
- Sébrier, M., Siame, L., Zouine, E. M., Winter, T., Missenard, Y., Leturmy P., 2006. Active tectonics in the Moroccan High Atlas. *Comptes Rendus Geosciences* 338, 65-79.
- Schildgen, T.F., Cosentino, D., Bookhagen, B., Niedermann, S., Yıldırım, C., Echtler, H., Wittmann, H. & Strecker, M.R., 2012. Multi-phased uplift of the southern margin of the Central Anatolian Plateau, Turkey: a record of tectonic and upper mantle processes. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 317–318, 85–95.
- Snyder, N.P., Whipple, K.X., Tucker, G.E., Merritts, D.J., 2002. Interactions between onshore bedrock-channel incision and nearshore wave-base erosion forced by eustasy and tectonics. *Basin Research* 14, 105-127.
- Sun, D., Miller, M.S., Holt, A.F., Becker, T.W., 2014. Hot upwelling conduit beneath the Atlas Mountains, Morocco. *Geophys. Res. Letters* 41 8037-8044.
- Teixell, A., Arboleya, M.L., Julivert, M., Charroud, M., 2003. Tectonic shortening and topography in the central High Atlas (Morocco). *Tectonics* 22, doi:10.1029/2002TC001460.
- Teixell, A., Ayarza, P., Zeyen, H., Fernandez, M., Arboleya, M.L., 2005. Effects of mantle upwelling in a compressional setting: the Atlas Mountains of Morocco. *Terra Nova* 17, 456–461.
- Whipple, K.X., 2001. Fluvial Landscape Response Time: How Plausible Is Steady-State Denudation?. *American Journal of Science* 301, 313-325.
- Whipple, K.X., Tucker, G.E., 1999. Dynamics of the stream-power river incision model: Implications for height limits of mountain ranges, landscape response timescales, and research needs. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 104(B8), 17,661-17,674.

Wobus, C., Whipple, K.X., Kirby, E., Snyder, N., Johnson, J., Spyropolou, K., Crosby, B., Sheehan, D., 2006. Tectonics from topography; procedures, promise, and pitfalls. Geological Society of America special Paper 398, 55-74.

Zeyen, H., Ayarza, P., Fernández, M., Rimi, A., 2005. Lithospheric structure under the western African-European plate boundary: a transect across the Atlas Mountains and the Gulf of Cadiz. *Tectonics* 24, doi:10.1029/2004TC001639.

Figures

Fig. 1. Digital elevation model (DEM SRTM90) of northeastern Morocco, with the main morphotectonic features and the Moulouya drainage basin. SMAFZ, Southern Middle Atlas frontal zone.

Fig. 2. a) Longitudinal profiles for the Moulouya river from the headwaters to the Mediterranean, and for its main tributaries, projected on the same plane. The color bar indicates the size of the upstream drainage area. **b)** Longitudinal profile of the Moulouya river in the Arhbalou and Missouri basins, showing a knickzone located 100-150 km from the headwaters. The reconstructed profile (using $K_s=21$ and $\theta=0.24$) shows a difference in elevation of 300-400 m with respect to the current river.

Fig. 3. Digital elevation model (DEM SRTM90) for the Missouri and Guercif basins (central segment of the Moulouya river). The river courses analyzed in this study are highlighted. The dashed white line marks the location of the topographic profile shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 4. (a) Longitudinal profiles for the Moulouya river and its tributaries with drainage areas over 50 km^2 projected on the same plane. Most of the tributaries draining the stable margin of the Missouri basin exhibit anomalously low gradients in their upper segments and similar knickzones in their long profiles. The prolongation of these upper segments allows reconstructing the basin paleosurface, which was 500-550 m above the current Moulouya river. (b) Long profile of the Kaddou river (see location in Figure 3) draining the stable margin of the Missouri basin; the red dashed line shows the reconstructed paleoprofile (using $K_s=13$ and $\theta=0.19$) that reaches 550 m over the current Moulouya river. (c) Long profile of the Fajane river (see location in Figure 3), the red dashed line showing the reconstructed paleoprofile with $K_s=83$ and $\theta=0.40$. The paleoprofile reaches 500 m over the Moulouya river. (d) Long profile of the Za river (see location in Figure 3) draining the High Plateaus to the Guercif basin, the red dashed line showing the reconstructed paleoprofile using $K_s=34$ and $\theta=0.26$, which reaches 450 m over the Moulouya river.

Fig. 5. (a) Longitudinal profile of the Chegg Ard river (see location in Figure 3) draining the Jebel Bou Naceur to the Missouri basin. The red dashed line shows the reconstructed paleoprofile (using $K_s=680$ and $\theta=0.62$) that reaches 1000 m over the current Moulouya river. (b) Satellite image from Google Earth of the mountainous segment of the Chegg Ard river. Upstream the channel flows along a wide valley; downwards the long profile exhibits a large knickpoint, downstream from which the channel is deeply incised. (c) Long profile of the El Mansoor river (see location in Figure 3) draining the Jebel Bou Naceur to the Guercif basin. The red dashed line shows the reconstructed paleoprofile (using $K_s=950$ and $\theta=0.62$) that reaches 750 m over the current Moulouya river. (d) Long profile of the El Berd and Timrhout rivers (see location in Figure 3) draining the Jebel Bou Naceur to the Guercif basin. The red dashed line shows the reconstructed paleoprofile (using $K_s=5722$ and $\theta=0.75$) that reaches 7200 m over the current Moulouya river. (e) Satellite image from Google Earth showing the mountainous segment of the Timrhout river blocked by a rock landslide, creating an abrupt knickpoint and the lake Gualta Tamda.

Fig. 6. (a) Google Earth image of the central Missouri basin and the Jebel Bou Naceur with the main geologic structures and rivers. (b) Close-up of the Chegg Ard valley showing the mapping of fluvial deposits and landforms, tectonic flexures, sampling points, and the trace of the profile in Figure 9 (red dashed line). CAF – Chegg Arg fault; MF -mountain front; BAA – Beni Aioun anticline; FMF - Frontal monocline.

Fig. 7. Views of terrace levels at the western side of the Chegg Ard from the fold crest of the Frontal monocline. (a) View to the SE where an alluvial fan surfaces T2 and T3 dominate. (b) View to the NE showing the terrace T1 in the background and T2, T3 and T4 preserved in the core of the Frontal monocline.

Fig. 8. Be-10 TCN ages for terrace levels T1 and T2. The horizontal black line and grey band are the mean and 1 σ values for each surface.

Fig. 9. Topographic profile traced parallel to the Chegg Ard river along its eastern margin (see Figure 6b for location). Surfaces T1 and T2 are projected in the same plane, in continuous line where preserved, and in dashed line were inferred. The figure shows the difference in elevation of terraces T1 and T2 with respect the active Chegg Ard channel at both sides of the tectonic structures. Are also shown are the incision rates in mm/a for each position.

Fig. 10. Topographic profile across the Missouri basin and its margins from the Jebel Bou Naceur range to the High Plateaus (see Figure 3 for location), with the longitudinal profiles of the Chegg Ard and Kaddou rivers projected in the same plane. The knickzone of the Kaddou river is 550 m high and is related to the regional uplift affecting the entire fluvial network, whereas there is 1000 m difference in elevation between the Chegg and Kaddou rivers knickzones, probably due to a combination of regional uplift and local (thrust-related) neotectonic uplift of the Jebel Bou Naceur.

Table 1. Sample numbers, descriptions, locations, ^{10}Be data, and ^{10}Be ages for surfaces in the Cherg Ard valley

Sample number	Surface	Lithology	Class size Height/width/length (cm)	Sample thickness (cm)	Latitude (°N)	Longitude (°E)	Altitude ¹ (m asl)	Topographic correction	^{10}Be concentration ² (atoms/g $\text{SiO}_2 \times 10^3$)	Age Time independent Lal (1991)/Stone (2000) ^{3,4} (ka)	Age Desilet et al (2003, 2006) ⁵ (ka)	Age Dunai (2001) ⁵ (ka)	Age Lifton et al. (2005) ⁵ (ka)	Age Time dependent Lal (1991)/Stone (2000) ⁵ (ka)	Age Time dependent Lal (1991)/Stone (2000) ⁵ applying 1.4 m/Ma erosion (ka)
M908	T1a	Quartzite	12/8/5	5	33.36906667	-3.880783333	1144	1	383±8	473.6±47.8 (11.5)	464.5±62.7	447.2±59.8	444.4±50.2	424.1±41.1	n/a
M909	T1a	Sandstone	35-long	5	33.36913333	-3.88035	1140	1	351±11	431.8±44.4 (14.9)	421.9±57.3	404.5±54.4	401.5±45.9	385.5±38.2	n/a
M910	T1a	Sandstone	17/11/8	5	33.36906667	-3.88035	1143	1	351±9	430.7±43.6 (12.7)	420.5±56.5	403.2±53.8	400.3±45.2	384.5±37.5	n/a
M911	T1a	Sandstone	15/8/5	5	33.36893333	-3.879966667	1145	1	464±13	590.6±62.6 (18.9)	573.3±80.4	553.1±76.8	549.8±46.7	528.5±53.6	n/a
M912	T1a	Sandstone	10/8/05	5	33.36965	-3.879683333	1147	1	355±11	435.0±44.8 (15.0)	425.2±57.7	407.3±54.8	404.4±46.3	388.1±38.4	n/a
M913	T1a	Sandstone	15/10/5	5	33.36973333	-3.87945	1147	1	364±12	446.4±46.3 (16.0)	437.4±59.7	419.6±56.8	416.2±48.0	397.8±39.7	n/a
M915	T1b	Sandstone	14/10/5	5	33.37775	-3.896533333	1208	1	392±11	463.0±47.5 (14.5)	451.4±61.4	434.5±58.5	431.1±49.3	412.3±40.6	n/a
M916	T1b	Sandstone	17/10/6	6	33.37796667	-3.897616667	1212	1	363±9	427.0±43.1 (12.3)	413.4±55.4	397.4±52.8	394.4±44.4	380.3±36.9	n/a
M917	T1b	Sandstone	11/7/05	5	33.37855	-3.897766667	1211	0.8542	345±8	474.4±48.3 (12.9)	462.7±62.7	445.9±59.9	442.6±50.3	424.1±41.4	n/a
M918	T1b	Sandstone	15/11/5	5	33.37838333	-3.89695	1209	1	316±10	363.5±36.8 (12.4)	348.1±46.4	335.4±44.3	332.5±37.4	320.9±31.3	n/a
M919	T1b	Sandstone	11/9/04	4	33.37893333	-3.898333333	1214	1	451±15	534.1±56.9 (20.4)	521.0±72.9	501.3±69.5	498.1±58.8	478.6±49.0	n/a
Average														411±55	
M920	T2a	Sandstone	17/13/6	6	33.39696667	-3.905066667	1134	1	45±2	50.8±5.3 (2.7)	49.8±6.5	48.6±6.3	47.8±5.4	45.7±4.6	48.5±5.1
M921	T2a	Sandstone	13/7/4	4	33.39696667	-3.905083333	1135	1	73±2	81.5±7.5 (1.9)	80.9±9.9	78.6±9.6	77.8±8.0	74.3±6.6	81.7±8.1
M922	T2a	Sandstone	13/8/6	6	33.39696667	-3.905	1135	1	51±3	57.3±5.8 (2.9)	57.1±7.4	55.6±7.2	54.7±6.1	51.9±5.2	55.8±5.9
M923	T2a	Sandstone	15/12/7	7	33.39673333	-3.905066667	1134	1	59±3	67.5±6.8 (3.2)	67.0±8.7	65.4±8.4	64.7±7.2	61.8±6.1	66.6±7.1
M924	T2a	Sandstone	9/7/06	7	33.3967	-3.9048	1135	1	69±5	79.3±9.5 (6.4)	78.6±11.4	76.4±11.0	75.6±9.7	72.3±8.5	79.2±10.3
M925	T2a	Sandstone	12/8/05	5	33.39643333	-3.90445	1134	1	42±10	47.0±12.0 (11.2)	46.0±12.3	45.1±12.0	44.4±11.5	42.6±10.8	44.8±12.0
M926	T2b	Siltstone	26/18/7	7	33.35616667	-3.856266667	1018	0.8542	236±10	368.5±39.3 (17.5)	360.2±49.6	345.8±47.2	343.6±40.4	327.8±33.8	671.5±193.2
M927	T2b	Phyllite	7/7/07	7	33.35606667	-3.856516667	1021	1	92±3	116.4±11.3 (4.5)	113.7±14.5	110.7±14.0	109.7±11.9	105.1±10.0	119.7±13.2
M928	T2b	Sandstone	20/7/7	7	33.35596667	-3.857266667	1022	1	48±2	59.8±5.8 (2.5)	60.2±7.6	58.7±7.4	57.9±6.3	54.6±5.2	58.8±6.0
M929	T2b	Sandstone	20/10/4	4	33.35536667	-3.855733333	1016	1	17±1	21.1±2.1 (1.0)	22.7±2.8	22.4±2.9	22.1±2.4	20.4±2.0	20.9±2.1
M930	T2b	Sandstone	18/8/5	5	33.35615	-3.857966667	1021	1	69±3	84.5±8.2 (3.3)	84.6±10.7	82.2±10.4	81.4±8.8	77.3±7.3	85.3±9.0
M932	T2b	Sandstone	16/8/6	6	33.35588333	-3.853433333	1012	1	19±2	22.7±2.7 (1.9)	24.3±3.5	24.0±3.5	23.7±3.1	22.0±2.6	22.5±2.7
Average⁶														52±20	

¹Altitudes were determined using a handheld GPS with an uncertainty of ±30 m.²Six blanks were measured with $^{10}\text{Be}/^9\text{Be}$ ratio = $4.24 \pm 2.3 \times 10^{-14}$ ³Ages were determined using a rock density of 2.75 g/cm³ and 07KNSTD standard. Uncertainties include analytical and production rate/scale model uncertainties.⁴Uncertainty includes analytical and production rates and uncertainty in parenthesis is only analytical⁵Samples M926 and M927 were not included in average